
MANAGING THE CONFLUENCE OF PATENT LAW AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE - OBSTACLES AND SOLUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INDIA WITH USA

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ABSTRACT

AI is quickly approaching a tipping point in its growth that will affect a wide range of industries, including business, healthcare, and agriculture. While the enhanced capabilities of AI hold immense potential for beneficial outcomes, they also pose a substantial threat to the current legal structures governing patents. The implications of this issue on creativity, economic growth, and society at large are profound². Because of this, it is essential that all relevant parties—lawmakers, academics, and patent professionals—hold in-depth conversations to develop strategies for promoting innovation and resolving the complex legal difficulties resulting from patent law within the context of artificial intelligence³. The stakes are quite high, and if these problems are not resolved, terrible things might happen. In light of the current environment, this study examines many facets of patent law as they relate to AI inventions. These include the eligibility criteria for patents, the patentability of AI in the US and India, and the broader ramifications of the combination of patent law and AI. The paper offers a comparative analysis of these two nations' legal systems, pointing out the similarities and differences in each system's perception of artificial intelligence. The paper offers

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² von Struensee S, 'Artificial Intelligence and Corporate Social Responsibility' (SSRN, 6 July 2021) <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3873097> accessed 22 April 2024

³ ((PDF) unbox the black-box for the medical explainable AI via multi-modal and multi-centre Data Fusion: A mini-review, two showcases and beyond)<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353621660_Unbox_the_black-box_for_the_medical_explainable_AI_via_multi-modal_and_multi-centre_data_fusion_A_mini-review_two_showcases_and_beyond> accessed 22 April 2024

some suggestions for modernizing legal frameworks to take into account the quick developments in AI. The paper highlights the importance of constant communication and cooperation between all parties involved to ensure that innovation flourishes in this fascinating and rapidly developing subject. It does this by concentrating on the difficulties that result from the relationship between AI and patent law.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Ownership, Patent Laws, Innovations, AI-Patentability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The swift progress of developing technologies, particularly artificial intelligence (AI), has significantly influenced various sectors and the community at large in the recent past. This development has brought up several legal and moral concerns, especially those about intellectual property rights and, in particular, patent laws⁴. Patent laws are the driving factor behind invention and technological progress. Most of the time, a patent is a form of legal exclusivity that grants the owner the sole right to produce, use, and market an invention for a certain period, usually 20 years from the date of application. Because of this exclusive right, innovators are encouraged to create and enhance new products and procedures because it guarantees they will benefit and recoup their investment⁵.

In addition, patent regulations promote competition and knowledge exchange, which benefits the general public. The patent system guarantees that innovative ideas are shared and can be further developed in the future by others by requiring inventors to fully disclose their ideas in their patent applications. Ultimately, this process drives economic expansion and new technological developments.

⁴'The Patent Crisis and How the Courts Can Solve It' (*University of Chicago Press*, 1 May 2009) <<https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/P/bo6637375.html>> accessed 22 April 2024

⁵ (*NBER*) <<https://www.nber.org/system/files/chapters/c2144/c2144.pdf>> accessed 26 April 2024

In addition, the patent system offers a framework for settling disputes over the ownership and infringement of innovations. By taking this action, innovators can safeguard their intellectual property and stop others from unfairly making money off of their creations, creating a more level playing field that encourages competition and creativity⁶.

AI is permeating more and more sectors of the economy, which emphasizes the need to review current patent regulations and how they apply to AI-driven concepts. Through process simplification and efficiency gains, artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to completely transform several industries, including manufacturing, transportation, healthcare, and agriculture. AI is being used more and more in these sectors, which has resulted in the development of inventive and creative systems, goods, and processes that might qualify for patent protection. However, the development of artificial intelligence (AI) and other cutting-edge technologies has created new challenges for the administration of patent restrictions. Because of its special abilities, artificial intelligence can grow and learn on its own, which raises questions about the standard conditions for patentability, like originality and non-obviousness. There is also disagreement over whether AI counts as an invention in and of itself.

In addition, the legal questions about the ownership and infringement of AI-powered creations are becoming increasingly complicated. It might be challenging to determine who owns an invention or to place responsibility for patent infringement when AI is employed in collaborative, international research and development. These challenges necessitate a review of the existing patent laws and their application to artificial intelligence advances⁷. To ensure that innovators and inventors in the artificial intelligence area are adequately protected, patent rules must keep up with technical advancements.

AI-related patent rules necessitate a multifaceted strategy that considers the interests of investors, the public, and inventors, among other stakeholders. This plan would support the growth of the AI industry by promoting innovation and stabilizing and streamlining the patent system.

⁶ (NBER) <<https://www.nber.org/system/files/chapters/c2144/c2144.pdf>> accessed 26 April 2024

⁷ Btlj, 'Volume 36, Design Patents Symposium' (*Berkeley Technology Law Journal*, 17 January 2023) <<https://btlj.org/2022/02/volume-36-design-patents-symposium/>> accessed 26 April 2024

This article's goal is to provide a thorough examination of the current state of AI-related patent laws in the US and India in light of the previous discussion. Additionally, a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and opportunities presented by applying patent laws to artificial intelligence—including the intricate problems of patentability, ownership, and infringement—will be conducted. The paper will assess the benefits and drawbacks of the existing patent systems in the US and India in light of AI-related issues. It will also estimate the effects of these changes on the enforcement and protection of AI-related inventions by referencing recent legislative and case law developments in both countries.

Finally, the research will provide valuable perspectives on how these governments' AI-related patent rules may evolve in the future. The article's objective is to develop a new legal framework that balances the interests of investors, inventors, and the general public while addressing the ethical and societal implications of artificial intelligence (AI) and promoting innovation. This will add to the present discussion at the nexus of patent law and artificial intelligence and inform stakeholders and decision-makers about potential future orientations of this rapidly evolving sector.

II. PATENTING AI: POSSIBILITIES AND CHALLENGES

The field of artificial intelligence has expanded rapidly in recent years. An increasing number of legal questions about ownership, patentability, and infringement are brought up by the corpus of AI-driven ideas. Owing to these legal difficulties, safeguarding inventors and successfully resolving legal disagreements need examining several issues. Completing the necessary conditions for patentability is a significant barrier to patenting AI-related innovations. An invention must meet certain criteria, such as novelty, non-obviousness, and utility, to be given a patent.

However, given the nature of AI technology, it can be challenging to judge if an AI-related innovation complies with these requirements. One of the primary barriers to AI inventions being eligible for patent protection is the non-obviousness criteria⁸. Large data volumes are frequently

⁸ R; Y-RS, 'Summoning a New Artificial Intelligence Patent Model: In the Age of Pandemic' (*SSRN*) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32714121/>> accessed 26 April 2024

analyzed by artificial intelligence (AI) technology, which also produces creative answers to difficult problems. It can be more challenging to satisfy the non-obviousness criteria when answers produced by AI systems appear clear to subject matter experts. Furthermore, because AI systems usually rely on data that already exists, it may be challenging to establish the uniqueness of a concept. For instance, it might be difficult to demonstrate that an invention is novel when an AI system is trained on pre-existing data sets to find patterns or provide solutions. This is because the innovation is dependent on data that has already been gathered.

Proposals have been made to amend the patent laws to solve these issues. For example, some experts have proposed modifying the non-obviousness criteria to account for AI's role in the process of creation.

Moreover, there have been demands for AI systems to be recognized as inventors, leading to a major revision of the current patent laws⁹.

Furthermore, the complicated issue of who owns inventions related to artificial intelligence has received a lot of attention lately. This complexity arises from the possibility that new products and solutions can be created using artificial intelligence (AI) technology with little to no human input. This leads to questions about whose intellectual property is connected to these technologies. One of the most difficult ownership issues is identifying the original creator of an artificial intelligence breakthrough. The person who developed the idea or invention is usually referred to as the inventor or creator under traditional patent law. However, it can be difficult to identify the designer of AI systems.

The individual or team in charge of creating the AI system may occasionally assert ownership of any inventions produced by the system. However, this approach disregards the AI system's contributions, which might have been crucial to the creative process.

⁹ Yanisky-Ravid S and Liu X (Jackie), 'When Artificial Intelligence Systems Produce Inventions: The 3A Era and an Alternative Model for Patent Law' (*SSRN*, 11 January 2022)
<https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2931828> accessed 26 April 2024

Additionally, there can be instances where the third party owns the data that was used to train the AI system. In certain cases, figuring out who is the rightful owner of the intellectual property rights to the resulting inventions may be challenging. To address these issues, proposals to modify intellectual property rules about AI have surfaced. As an example, some experts have proposed creating a new legal framework that acknowledges the contributions made to the creation process by both human and AI producers. Some advocate granting legal personhood to artificial intelligence (AI) systems, thereby endowing them with intellectual property rights.

Furthermore, infringement of AI-related inventions is a complicated matter that occurs when a third party uses, produces, or sells an invention without the patent owner's consent. As AI is applied in more and more industries, there is a higher risk of patent infringement. The issues of artificial intelligence and innovation infringement are discussed in the points that follow¹⁰.

Determining the level of protection that AI-related patents offer is the primary challenge. AI-related ideas could involve hardware, software, and data—all of which are often hard to distinguish from one another. Determining the invention's protected characteristics and the scope of the patent protection may therefore be challenging.

Another difficulty is figuring out whether using an innovation related to artificial intelligence is an infringement. Determining whether the output of an AI system trained on patent-protected data breaches the patent, for instance, may be challenging. In a similar vein, it can be challenging to ascertain whether an AI system used to create a novel good or process violates any existing patents¹¹.

A further concern is the possibility of inadvertent infringement. Systems using artificial intelligence (AI) may be built to perform certain tasks that unintentionally infringe upon patents. The patent owner may have a strong case for infringement in several situations, even if the infringement was unintentional.

¹⁰ R; Y-RS, 'Summoning a New Artificial Intelligence Patent Model: In the Age of Pandemic' (*SSRN*) <<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32714121/>> accessed 26 April 2024

¹¹ Kim D, "'Ai-Generated Inventions': Time to Get the Record Straight?' (*OUP Academic*, 8 June 2020) <<https://academic.oup.com/grurint/article/69/5/443/5854752>> accessed 26 April 2024

Furthermore, it may be difficult to assign blame for infringement when it comes to concepts about artificial intelligence. When an AI system is used to do a task that violates a patent, for example, it might be challenging to determine who is at fault—the AI system's creator, user, or owner.

There have been plans to create new legal frameworks that take into account the special qualities of inventions related to artificial intelligence to address these issues. For instance, some experts have proposed developing a system known as patent pooling, in which many patent owners can share their inventions, to lessen the chance of infringement. Some have suggested employing AI to detect potential patent infringement and boost the efficiency of patent lawsuits.

III. ANALYZING AI PATENT LAWS' SOCIAL AND ETHICAL REPERCUSSIONS

The social and ethical implications of AI for patent laws are diverse and intricate. On the one hand, artificial intelligence (AI) has the power to transform a wide range of sectors and enhance people's lives in numerous ways. However, concerns have been raised regarding the possible drawbacks of AI, including the loss of jobs, increased inequality, and the potential for misuse of the technology for harmful purposes¹².

One ethical worry about patent laws and AI is the possibility that it could make injustices that already exist worse.

For instance, a small group of wealthy corporations or individuals may monopolize the patents on AI-related innovations, increasing inequality and restricting access to the benefits of AI for those who cannot afford them. Concerns have also been raised about how AI may perpetuate bias and discrimination by using biased datasets or algorithms that disproportionately hurt specific groups.

Further ethical questions are raised by the prospect that AI would automate tasks that were previously performed by humans, leading to job losses and economic instability. While artificial intelligence (AI) has promise for boosting productivity and efficiency, there are worries that technology could exacerbate current economic disparities and lead to widespread joblessness.

¹² Author links open overlay panelSofiat O. Abioye a and others, 'Artificial Intelligence in the Construction Industry: A Review of Present Status, Opportunities and Future Challenges' (*Journal of Building Engineering*, 5 October 2021) <<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352710221011578>> accessed 26 April 2024

There have also been worries expressed about the potential misuse of AI for evil purposes, such as developing weapons that can fight for themselves or monitoring people without their knowledge.

It's also important to consider how AI will significantly impact patent laws in society. For instance, there are worries about AI's potential use in intellectual property theft and its impact on creativity and innovation. There are also worries about the negative uses of AI, such as conducting hacks or producing deep fake movies¹³.

Given these ethical and societal implications, legislators and legal professionals must carefully examine AI's implications within the context of patent laws. This means creating new legal frameworks that address the unique challenges posed by artificial intelligence-related inventions and that also consider the potential ethical and societal ramifications of these advancements. It's also critical to take part in public discussions about AI's role in society and ensure that its benefits are distributed fairly. In the end, a careful examination of the moral and legal implications of patent laws is required to ensure that AI promotes public benefit.

IV. AI AND PATENT LAWS: UNDERSTANDING THE LEGAL LANDSCAPE

The distinct legal regimes that manage patents in the US and India lead to different approaches to AI-related patent rules.

In India, patents are granted for inventions that are new, not immediately obvious, and suitable for industrial use. The Indian Patent Act of 1970 establishes the legal basis for patent protection in India. The Act lays forth the standards for invention eligibility as well as the processes for submitting, evaluating, and awarding patents¹⁴. Additionally, as long as an invention satisfies the requirements for patentability, the Act covers certain types of inventions, such as software and computer programs. In India, there is considerable debate about whether discoveries connected to

¹³ Brundage M and others, 'The Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence: Forecasting, Prevention, and Mitigation' (*arXiv.org*, 20 February 2018) <<https://arxiv.org/abs/1802.07228>> accessed 26 April 2024

¹⁴ (*The Patents Act, 1970*) <https://ipindia.gov.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOAct/1_31_1_patent-act-1970-11march2015.pdf> accessed 26 April 2024

AI should be eligible for patent protection. Some claim that the nation's current patent system might not be sufficient to address the unique characteristics of AI.

In the US, a patent may be applied for any novel and practical device, method, manufacture, composition of matter, or improvement thereof. The U.S. Patent Act of 1952¹⁵ created the legal framework for patent protection in the United States. The Act outlines the necessary conditions, such as usefulness, novelty, and non-obviousness, to qualify for a patent. Over the years, the U.S. Supreme Court has rendered several decisions that have clarified how these principles need to be applied to various developments, including software and business processes. In addition, the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office has published guidelines specifically on the patentability of inventions related to artificial intelligence.

Despite having differing legal systems, both the US and India acknowledge the importance of patent protection in fostering innovation and technological growth. Consequently, both nations have enhanced their patent systems to address the difficulties brought about by cutting-edge innovations like artificial intelligence. One example of a recent legislative change in India intended to improve transparency and expedite the patent application process is the 2020 update to the Patents Rules¹⁶.

In response to the unique challenges presented by AI-related innovations, the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office has launched pilot projects and created guidelines domestically¹⁷. These legal frameworks need to be continually reviewed and updated in light of the development of AI and other cutting-edge technologies to ensure that they maintain their ability to foster innovation while resolving the challenges associated with advancements related to AI.

¹⁵ (*Legislative IP acts (LIPA) / history archive: The patent act of ...*)
<https://ipmall.law.unh.edu/sites/default/files/hosted_resources/lipa/patents/patentact.asp> accessed 26 April 2024

¹⁶Drishiti IAS, 'Patents (Amendment) Rules, 2024' (*Drishiti IAS*, 27 March 2024) <<https://www.drishitias.com/daily-updates/daily-news-analysis/patents-amendment-rules-2024>> accessed 26 April 2024

¹⁷ (*USPTO*) <https://www.uspto.gov/sites/default/files/documents/2019_USPTO_BM_101-2019_PEG.pdf> accessed 26 April 2024

V. APPLICABILITY OF IP LAWS TO AI-RELATED INNOVATIONS IN INDIA

AI is being employed in an increasing number of businesses, hence the question of whether AI-related ideas are patentable has lately come up for discussion. The rules and regulations governing the patent systems of the United States and India may lead to different approaches to applying patent laws to AI-related inventions.

One of the numerous technical innovations included in India's development plan is artificial intelligence. Along with social media and entertainment, AI is being used more and more in retail. The adoption of online auto services and online commerce led to a dramatic upheaval in the country's technological landscape. The issues are far more severe in emerging countries like India since the basic infrastructure needs to be updated. Copyright and patent laws are well-established in India.

However, there isn't a special legislation or provision that deals with AI. The existing regulations do not take artificial intelligence into account and are based on antiquated definitions of intellectual property, which include books, creative writing, and discoveries. Because AI is so much more sophisticated than it is now handled, handling it calls for a different strategy.

According to Section 3(k) of The Patents Act of 1970, computer programs, business processes, and mathematical formulas are not considered patentable inventions¹⁸.

Furthermore, the phrase "patentee" under Section 2 (p)¹⁹ and "person interested" under Section 2 (t)²⁰ present a challenge to bringing AI under the ambit of the previously mentioned Act. The Act states unequivocally that any other person with an interest in humanity qualifies as the patentee.

The Indian Patent Office has approved patents for machine learning algorithms, neural networks, and natural language processing techniques. In 2017, the Indian government proposed amending

¹⁸ Monika_Verma, 'Non Patentable Inventions under the Patent Act' (*iPleaders*, 15 February 2019) <<https://blog.iPLEaders.in/non-patentable-inventions/>> accessed 26 April 2024

¹⁹ (*Section 2 in the Patents Act, 1970*) <<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/65643/>> accessed 26 April 2024

²⁰ (*Section 2 in the Patents Act, 1970*) <<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/65643/>> accessed 26 April 2024

the Patents Act to bring the country's patent laws into compliance with global standards and encourage greater innovation and investment in the technology sector by permitting the patenting of computer programs and other relevant content, such as artificial intelligence²¹.

The Copyright Act defines an original work according to two main theories: the Modicum of Creativity and the Sweat of the Brow Doctrine.²² Since the theory permits a certain amount of inventiveness, the original artificial intelligence work can be incorporated. Nonetheless, the "author" of the work is entitled to copyright under section 2(d) of the Act²³. Since the act's creator is identified as a human or legal person, the notion that a machine would be protected by it is constrained.

In the United States, the Patent Act's criteria are used by the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) to decide whether ideas relating to artificial intelligence (AI) are eligible for patent protection. According to the Patent Act, any "new and useful process, machine, manufacture, or composition of matter" is eligible for patent protection. Patent examiners can evaluate an AI-related invention's eligibility for patent protection based on several criteria, including the invention's novelty, non-obviousness, utility, and subject matter eligibility. The USPTO has published these guidelines.

However, it can be challenging to apply patent laws to AI-related ideas due to the complexity and rapid evolution of AI technology. Artificial intelligence (AI) inventions can be difficult to assess for uniqueness and non-obviousness, and there's a danger that less-than-useful or unoriginal technology won't be granted patents.

Both in the US and India, there have been calls for reform and greater clarification regarding the patentability of inventions relating to AI. India has to align the Patents Act with international

²¹ (*Guidelines for examination of computer related ...*)

<https://www.ipindia.gov.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOGuidelinesManuals/1_86_1_Revised__Guidelines_for_Examination_of_Computer-related_Inventions_CRI_.pdf> accessed 26 April 2024

²² 'Doctrine of Originality in Copyright' (*Khurana and Khurana*)

<<https://www.khuranaandkhurana.com/2019/04/16/doctrine-of-originality-in-copyright/>> accessed 26 April 2024

²³ (*Section 2(d) in the Copyright Act, 1957*) <<https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1655540/>> accessed 26 April 2024

standards to encourage greater innovation and investment in the technology sector. The United States needs to create more precise laws and guidelines regarding the patentability of inventions connected to artificial intelligence to ensure that patents are only granted for truly innovative and useful discoveries.

VI. COMPARISON OF THE AI-PATENT REGIMES IN INDIA AND THE USA

1. Ownership

- **India** - In India, the legitimate owner of a patent is either the inventor or their employer, barring special circumstances.
- **USA** - In the US, an inventor or inventors often own the patent. If an innovation was made by an employee while they were working for a company, the employer may be the owner of the rights.

2. Inventorship

- **India** - According to the Indian Patent Act, an inventor in India is someone who helps with the ideation process. However, the Act provides no guidance on inventorship in the context of AI.
- **USA** - In the United States, demonstrating the origin of an invention requires naming the individual or people who contributed to its conceptualization. If an AI system is the only creator of an idea, it cannot be considered an inventor under current U.S. patent law.

3. Eligibility for Patents

- **India** - The eligibility of inventions involving AI for patent protection is governed by the Indian Patent Act, which does not specifically address AI. On the other hand, AI inventions are considered to fall under the category of computer-related

inventions (CRIs) and are eligible for patent protection under the same guidelines as other CRIs.

- **USA** - In the US, patent protection for AI inventions is contingent upon meeting three criteria: novelty, non-obviousness, and utility.

VII. CASE LAWS

India - India's rapid growth in the artificial intelligence (AI) area can be attributed to two factors: a rapidly expanding IT industry and a government that strongly prioritizes the development of AI-related technology. Like any emerging technology, there are potential benefits and major challenges associated with applying patent rules to AI-related ideas in India. A few sample studies that highlight some of these challenges and opportunities are as follows:

- Tata Consultancy Services is at odds over an AI patent. (TCS) ²⁴

In 2018, Seven Networks, an American IT business, filed a lawsuit against TCS, claiming that the latter had infringed upon a patent related to mobile messaging technology. TCS argued that the application of AI algorithms was obvious and not novel, so the patent was invalid.

This case emphasizes the challenges associated with patentability and infringement with AI-related ideas, underscoring the need to maintain patent laws up to date with rapidly advancing technologies.

- **India's Government's AI Patent Policy**

In 2020, the Indian government presented a proposed national AI plan that contained elements for an AI patent regime. To encourage the advancement and commercialization of AI-related technologies, the strategy suggests a variety of actions, including creating an AI patent pool and a legislative framework for AI patent licensing. This case emphasizes the potential benefits of governments

²⁴ Hebbar P, 'TCS' Ai-Powered Ignio Plans to Touch \$100 Million in Revenue within 2 Years' (*Analytics India Magazine*, 10 August 2018) <<https://analyticsindiamag.com/tcs-ai-powered-ignio-plans-to-touch-100-million-in-revenue-within-2-years/>> accessed 26 April 2024

actively promoting the development and ownership of cutting-edge technologies.

USA - As evidenced by several notable cases in the US, there are both opportunities and challenges associated with applying patent laws to AI-related discoveries. One example of this type is

- **Thaler v. US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO)²⁵:**

In a historic ruling, the USPTO denied patent applications for ideas created using an AI system known as DABUS, holding that even the most naturally talented individuals may be inventors. The decision was upheld by the U.S. District Court, emphasizing how the current patent system is human-centric (Fleming, 2007).

This case brings attention to the issues of AI ownership and identifying the inventor of an invention produced by AI. It also begs the question of whether patent rules should be modified to take into account new technological advancements or if they are still sufficient to handle concepts generated by AI.

These cases highlight the intricate legal problems that occur when AI-related inventions are subject to US patent laws and highlight the importance of carefully weighing the ethical and societal implications of AI technology development and regulation.

Getting Ready for AI Patent Laws: A Review of Recent Amendments in the USA and India

Artificial intelligence (AI) is developing at a rapid pace, which has created new concerns around patentability, ownership, and infringement of AI-related ideas, as well as substantial challenges to current patent policies. Consequently, several countries—including the US and India—have updated their legal frameworks to address these issues²⁶.

²⁵ (USPTO) <https://www.uspto.gov/sites/default/files/documents/16524350_22apr2020.pdf> accessed 26 April 2024

²⁶Liu H-Y and others, 'Artificial Intelligence and Legal Disruption: A New Model for Analysis' (SSRN, 7 February 2021) <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3761620> accessed 26 April 2024

New sections of the Patents (Amendment) Rules, 2020²⁷ in India have been included to speed up the patent application procedure for innovations related to artificial intelligence. These laws state that inventions that make use of AI or machine learning techniques may be submitted as patent applications as long as they meet the requirements for originality, creativity, and practicality in the business sector. Furthermore, the criteria require applicants to disclose the specifics of any AI or machine learning methods used in the production.

The Indian Patent Office has established guidelines for the assessment of computer-related innovations, which include cover discoveries connected to artificial intelligence. These standards provide a framework for assessing the technical contributions, originality, inventiveness, and industrial relevance of an invention to determine its patentability²⁸.

The patentability of software and ideas related to artificial intelligence has been profoundly impacted by the US Supreme Court's 2014 ruling in *Alice Corp. v. CLS Bank International*²⁹. The Court determined that laws of nature, natural phenomena, and abstract concepts are not patentable and that any application of these principles to technology needs to be focused on a specific technological application or method.

Following the *Alice* verdict, the USPTO published guidelines on the patentability of AI-related innovations, emphasizing the necessity for the invention to be focused on a specific technological application rather than just an abstract concept or algorithm. Furthermore, the USPTO published

²⁷ (*Official website of Intellectual Property India*) <<https://www.ipindia.gov.in/rules-patents.htm>> accessed 26 April 2024

²⁸ (*Guidelines for examination of computer related ...*)
<https://www.ipindia.gov.in/writereaddata/Portal/IPOGuidelinesManuals/1_86_1_Revised__Guidelines_for_Examination_of_Computer-related_Inventions_CRI_.pdf> accessed 26 April 2024

²⁹ 'The Federal Register' (*Federal Register :: Request Access*)
<<https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2019/01/07/2018-28283/examining-computer-implemented-functional-claim-limitations-for-compliance-with-35-usc-112>> accessed 26 April 2024

a letter that guides how to assess whether an invention is eligible for patent protection for examiners reviewing patent applications related to artificial intelligence (AI)³⁰.

These modifications to patent laws would have a substantial effect on the defense and enforcement of AI-related inventions in the US and India. For example, if there is clearer guidance on the patentability of concepts associated with artificial intelligence, inventors and enterprises can better understand their legal rights and take the necessary procedures to secure their intellectual property. Furthermore, these changes may encourage further investment and expansion in the AI sector by improving the predictability and stability of patent protection³¹.

However, there may be implications for future developments of patent laws about artificial intelligence. For instance, as AI technology advances, fresh problems and worries regarding the patentability of AI-related concepts can come up. In addition, cultural and ethical issues around who owns and utilizes AI-related technology may also need to be addressed.

In conclusion, the recent changes to US and Indian patent rules have significant implications not just for the future of patent laws related to AI, but also for the protection and enforcement of discoveries associated with AI. As AI technology develops, legislators and patent experts will need to adapt and enhance patent laws as needed to ensure proper protection, promote innovation, and address moral and societal issues.

³⁰ ‘Artificial Intelligence and Patent Law: Navigating the Landscape in 2023: Article: Chambers and Partners’ (*Article | Chambers and Partners*) <<https://chambers.com/articles/artificial-intelligence-and-patent-law-navigating-the-landscape-in-2023>> accessed 26 April 2024

³¹ Selenko E and others, ‘Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Work: A Functional-Identity Perspective’ (*University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign*, 18 July 2022) <<https://experts.illinois.edu/en/publications/artificial-intelligence-and-the-future-of-work-a-functional-identity>> accessed 26 April 2024

VIII. CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence is rapidly evolving and transforming numerous sectors. As AI grows increasingly essential, strict patent laws will become more and more critical to safeguard and foster innovation in this industry. While the US leads the world in AI development, other countries like India are also making great progress in this field.

Consequently, it is imperative to investigate potential future directions for AI-related patent regulations in India using a comparison analysis with the United States.

The American legal system is sophisticated and dynamic, always adapting to the needs of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence. The US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) has published guidelines that state that inventions relating to artificial intelligence must satisfy the same standards for patentability as any other invention. In addition, instructions for evaluating AI-related patent applications—such as those involving natural language processing (NLP) and machine learning (ML)—have been made public by the USPTO.

India has made notable advancements in the field of artificial intelligence, aided by multiple government initiatives promoting AI research and development. Meanwhile, criticism has been leveled at the Indian patent system for its sluggish and inefficient functioning. Because it could result in inconsistent patent approvals, the ambiguity of the patentability requirements for AI-related technologies has also garnered criticism.

To solve these issues, India might take a cue from the US's best practices in AI-related patent legislation. The Indian Patent Office (IPO) may release rules for evaluating AI-related patent applications that are comparable to those of the USPTO. The IPO may maybe think about hiring a special team of examiners with knowledge of AI to ensure uniformity in the evaluation of patent applications related to the technology.

India might consider introducing artificial intelligence (AI) into the patent review process. AI can assist patent examiners in analyzing patent claims and conducting previous art searches. This can help clear the backlog of patent applications and provide a prompt and efficient evaluation of applications related to artificial intelligence.

In the future, Indian patent rules will need to be adjusted to AI, which will require the application of US best practices. India should ensure equitable and uniform evaluation of AI-related patent applications by establishing guidelines for AI-related innovations, developing a team of skilled examiners, and incorporating AI into the patent examination procedure. This will protect innovators well and stimulate the economy in addition to promoting artificial intelligence research. Consequently, to adapt to future AI patent regulations and create an environment that would encourage AI research and growth, the Indian Patent Regime can implement several of these recommendations:

- **Clarity on conditions for patentability:** The Indian government should establish clear guidelines and standards for the patentability of ideas linked to artificial intelligence (AI) to remove any doubt and reassure businesses and inventors seeking patent protection.
- **Enhance the expertise of patent examiners:** To ensure that patents are examined and approved in a timely and efficient manner, India should assemble a team of examiners with a strong background in AI technology.
- **Promote industry-academia cooperation:** To foster innovation in AI-related fields, India should promote industry-academia cooperation. This would help to generate patentable AI concepts and offer assistance in resolving complex patent disputes.
- **Establish a strong legal framework:** India should establish a comprehensive legal framework with specific provisions for patents related to AI to ensure that inventions relating to AI are protected and swiftly enforced.
- **Educate SMEs and start-ups on intellectual property:** The Indian government ought to provide SMEs and start-ups with intellectual property education. As a result, there would be a rise in AI-related patent applications in India, giving Indian companies a competitive advantage in global markets.

- **Analyzing Global Cooperation and Patent Law Harmonization:** The role of international collaboration in the field of patent law must be investigated due to the impact and global reach of artificial intelligence (AI) technology. We suggest that future studies focus on the possibility of harmonizing patent laws across nations. By doing this, we can gain a better understanding of the issues surrounding patent law and artificial intelligence as well as possible solutions. Thanks to international discussion and negotiation, innovation and the protection of intellectual property rights could be bolstered by unified rules that take into account the unique characteristics of artificial intelligence.
- **Inclusion of Alternative Intellectual Property Protection Mechanisms:** In addition to patent laws, other intellectual property protection mechanisms such as trade secrets must be included to fully understand the options available for AI-related ideas. Future research could look at these alternative systems' advantages and disadvantages, as well as how they interact with patent laws and are applied in the field of artificial intelligence. In the era of rapid technological innovation, having a deeper awareness of the intellectual property landscape can help to promote a more nuanced discussion about intellectual property rights and give innovators more tools to protect their ideas.

Strong patent laws are increasingly necessary to safeguard and encourage innovation in this area as artificial intelligence (AI) continues to revolutionize numerous industries. India is also making great progress in AI, even if the US is leading the way in this area.

However, when examining patent applications relevant to artificial intelligence, the Indian patent system has to solve problems with uniformity, effectiveness, and clarity. By adopting US best practices, such as providing guidelines for AI-related innovations, putting together a team of skilled examiners, and integrating AI into the patent application process, India can foster an environment that is favorable to AI innovation and growth. These steps will ensure that India maintains its competitiveness in the global market, provide sufficient protection for innovators, and foster economic expansion.